

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 DOMAIN INTRODUCTION

Image Processing

Image Processing is a technique to enhance raw images received from cameras/sensors placed on space probes, aircraft and satellites or pictures taken in normal day-to-day life for various applications. An Image is a rectangular graphical object. Image processing involves issues related to image representation, compression techniques and various complex operations, which can be carried out on the image data. The operations that come under image processing are image enhancement operations such as sharpening, blurring, brightening, edge enhancement etc. Image processing is any form of signal processing for which the input is an image, such as photographs or frames of video; the output of image processing can be either an image or a set of characteristics or parameters related to the image. Most image-processing techniques involve treating the image as a two-dimensional signal and applying standard signal-processing techniques to it. Image processing usually refers to digital image processing, but optical and analogue image processing is also possible. Digital image processing is to process images by computer. Digital image processing mainly includes image collection, image processing, and image analysis. At its most basic level, a digital image processing system is comprised of three components, ie, a computer system on which to process images, an image digitizer, and an image display device.

Fundamentals of image processing

Image processing refers to the manipulation of digital images in order to extract more information than is actually visible on the original image.^{40,41} A digital image is a 2-D matrix of pixels of different values which define the colour or grey level of the image. The higher the resolution of an image, the greater the number of

pixels. Each pixel represents a variation in greys or colours. The grey level resolution is expressed in terms of bits; an 8-bit image has 256 grey levels.

Image processing techniques use filters to enhance an image. Their main applications are to transform the contrast, brightness, resolution and noise level of an image. Contouring, image sharpening, blurring, embossing and edge detection are typical image processing functions (see Table 4.1). Low and high pass filters (spatial filters) are used when the filtering is based on pixel values and gradients to smooth and reduce noise and details. High pass filters are used for edge enhancement and to sharpen an image. Low pass filters are used to smooth an image. Only a small number of image processing filters are necessary to obtain information about an image. Image processing operations can be performed in the spatial domain and frequency domain of an image. Spatial domain refers to the matrix of pixels composing an image (original pixels of the image). Frequency domain refers to the matrix of numbers making up a Fourier-transformed image (spectral representation of the image). Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is a powerful tool for analysis and computation in image processing and is used to compensate for imaging/optical effects. The 2-D FFT of an image identifies the spatial frequency components and eliminates suspected noise components in the transform. The inverse FFT is taken and a filtered image is produced.

Components of Image Processing System

Image Processing System is the combination of the different elements involved in the digital image processing. Digital image processing is the processing of an image by means of a digital computer. Digital image processing uses different computer algorithms to perform image processing on the digital images.

It consists of following components:-

- **Image Sensors:**

Image sensors senses the intensity, amplitude, co-ordinates and other features of the images and passes the result to the image processing hardware. It includes the problem domain.

- **Image Processing Hardware:**

Image processing hardware is the dedicated hardware that is used to process the instructions obtained from the image sensors. It passes the result to general purpose computer.

- **Computer:**

Computer used in the image processing system is the general purpose computer that is used by us in our daily life.

- **Image Processing Software:**

Image processing software is the software that includes all the mechanisms and algorithms that are used in image processing system.

- **Mass Storage:**

Mass storage stores the pixels of the images during the processing.

- **Hard Copy Device:**

Once the image is processed then it is stored in the hard copy device. It can be a pen drive or any external ROM device.

- **Image Display:**

It includes the monitor or display screen that displays the processed images.

- **Network:**

Network is the connection of all the above elements of the image processing system.

1.2 PROBLEM DEFINITION

Many residential society administrations, tolls, business complexes and parking spaces in India lack an automated system for car parking and vehicle monitoring. Most of the commercial and residential places face an impending problem of illegal car/vehicle parking inside their premises. This issue is not bounded to just parking, but also adds to the security concerns inside those establishments. Though there are solutions that exist in the market, the affordability comes into question. In this regard when a vehicle passes through a parking area and the solution

identifies as many features as it can regarding the situation of the vehicle. we build a factious database based on the vehicles appearing in footage and demonstrate the problems that they are able to solve/automate in existing infrastructure. (For example, if a team is trying to solve problems of a residential complex, they might create a database of some of the vehicles appearing in the footage and list them as residents and others not registered in the database to be considered as visitors).

1.3 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Intelligent Parking System can grant permission to access the parking area with less human inference. This system can capture image of the vehicle, identify the type of vehicle and allot best fit and optimal parking slot based on its size. It extracts the vehicle's License plate number, entry time, exit time and calculate total time of the vehicle present with in the parking space. camera is used to identify the Region of Interest, Vehicle license plate and identify the characters from the license plate. Tesseract Engine and Optical Character Recognition (OCR) functions are used to detect characters from the image. These days the quantity of vehicles is expanding exceptionally, so that, searching for an empty parking slot turns out to be increasingly troublesome. By installing the Intelligent Parking System, in places like, shopping malls, train stations, and airports the need for searching of parking slot significantly reduced. Smart parking system is an integrated system to organize cars in public parks using OCR . The system will be used for every slot in park. The motivation of this project is to help drivers. And make the payment way easier to detect the unauthorized vehicle in the slot.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

Automatic Parking Space Detection System

**Authors: Nazia Bibi ; Muhammad Nadeem Majid ; Hassan Dawood ; Ping Guo,
Year: 2017**

Searching a suitable parking space in populated metropolitan city is extremely difficult for drivers. Serious traffic congestion may occur due to unavailable parking space. Automatic smart parking system is emerging field and attracted computer vision researchers to contribute in this arena of technology. In this paper, we have presented a vision based smart parking framework to assist the drivers in efficiently finding suitable parking slot and reserve it. Initially, we have segmented the parking area into blocks using calibration. Then, classify each block to identify car and intimate the driver about the status of parking either reserved or free. Potentially, the performance accuracy of recommended system is higher than state of the art hardware solutions, validating the supremacy of the proposed framework.

Software Design of Automatic Parking Robot Based on Flat Stereo Garage

Authors: Dapeng Wang ; Jianwei Ye ; Chence Guo.

Year: 2019

This paper introduces an agv robot for automatic parking in a flat stereo garage. The agv is independently developed by our company and has the functions of driving along a fixed path, autonomous navigation, two-stage anti-collision, sound and light alarm. It is characterized by heavy load and can be used for automatic parking of all household models up to 2.5t. Fast driving speed up to 3m/s. It can spin in place without setting the turning radius, thus making the garage more compact and the car density can be increased by 65% compared with the ordinary garage. Automatically find the charging position and charge it, it can work 24 hours a day, greatly

improving the use and operation efficiency of the entire garage, greatly improving the economic and social benefits of the garage.

License Plate Detection and Integral Intensity Projection for Automatic Finding the Vacant of Car Parking Space

Authors: P. Choorat ; C. Sirikornkarn ; T. Pramoun.

Year:2019

This paper demonstrates approaches for automatic counting the number of car in a parking lot image by using the location of license plate area and the result of intensity projection. Firstly, in order to obtain the car height boundaries, we applied the edge processing histogram in a vertical direction. This histogram results from the total summation of difference intensity values between the pixel and it neighboring pixel of the enhanced image. Next, the result of derivative method is applied to segment the image into the region of interest (ROI). To estimate the license plate area, the edge processing histogram is utilized again along the horizontal direction. After that the integral intensity projection is applied to sum and smooth both intensity projection result of the histogram and the ROI image in vertical direction. Finally, the number of parking spots were detected and counted by using peak detection results. The accuracy for counting the number of cars in the indoor parking lot image is 81.16% by applying these techniques.

Automatic Car Parking System Using Raspberry-Pi with Cloud Storage Environment

Authors: R Aswini. ; T Archana,

Year: 2019

In the present world, the increasing number of vehicles along with irregular parking leads to traffic congestion in many areas. But the existing system defines uses wide range of sensors to regulate it. In automatic parking system enables driver to locate

the available parking slot even in traffic congestion area using Raspberry-pi and stores the data of the driver in cloud to enable scalability and accessibility. Each authenticated user uses their own allocated slot and the others are provided with different available slot. The available slots are provided to the user in any range of accessing the parking slot.

AU Automatic Car-Parking Modeling System

Authors: Narong Aphiratsakun ; Lam Thanh Duy ; Jiradech Kongthon.

Year: 2018

This article presents the AU Automatic Car-Parking Modeling System, hereafter referred to as the AU-CPS. The AU-CPS is a model of an automatic parking system controlled by PLC. It interacts with the user via HMI, driven by three DC motors with the use of photo-electric sensors. A crane is used to lift and take the car from an initial to parking slot and from a parking slot to the exit way. The AU-CPS also shows whether parking is full or not by turning on an LED, and it uses sensors to detect the car in the slot to avoid overlapping in each slot.

Automatic Parking Trajectory Planning Based on Recurrent Neural Network

Authors: Zhonghan Wang ; Qingliang Shao ; Chen Wang ; Qian Zhang.

Year: 2018

Relying on a company's automatic parking project, This paper proposes a method which use TensorFlow training Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) to predict parking trajectory curves and determine the optimal parking trajectory. First, we established a parallel parking model with obstacles and gave the starting point of the parking and the range of obstacles. Then use the arctangent function to discretize the model parking trajectory and introduce the discretized data as initial sample data into TensorFlow for Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) training to generate discretized parking trajectory curve data. Finally, the data will be summed into the actual parking

trajectory curve and compared with the experienced driver parking trajectory curve. It is found that the parking trajectory curve which obtained by the method proposed in this paper is highly integrated with the rich driver parking trajectory curve, and even exceeded in the obstacle avoidance function.

An IoT-based E-parking system for smart cities

Authors: Pampa Sadhukhan.

Year: 2017

The increasing number of vehicles on the road along with the mismanagement of available parking space leads to the parking related problems as well as increased traffic congestion in urban areas. Thus it is highly required to develop an automated smart parking management system that would help the driver to find out some suitable parking space for his/her vehicle very quickly. Although ample amount of research works on the development of smart parking system exist in literature, but most of them have not addressed the problem of real-time detection of improper parking and automatic collection of parking charges. In this paper, a prototype of internet-of-thing based E-parking system is proposed. The proposed E-parking system uses an integrated component called parking meter to address the above-mentioned issues as well as to provide smart parking management throughout the city.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

In existing system they have used IoT based model for automatic parking system but that was not more efficient because they have used more hardware components and it's having some drawbacks, There is a greater construction cost per space (but this may be offset by the chance for lesser land costs per space and the system manufacturers say that the operating and maintenance cost will be lower as compared to a conventional cramped parking structure). Most of the commercial and residential places face an impending problem of illegal car/vehicle parking inside their premises. This issue is not bounded to just parking, but also adds to the security concerns inside those establishments. Though there are solutions that exist in the market, the affordability comes into question. In this regard when a vehicle passes through a parking area and the solution identifies as many features as it can regarding the situation of the vehicle

3.1.1 DRAWBACKS OF EXISTING SYSTEM

- 1) **Security:** As the IoT systems are interconnected and communicate over networks. The system offers little control despite any security measures, and it can be lead the various kinds of network attacks.
- 2) **Privacy:** Even without the active participation on the user, the IoT system provides substantial personal data in maximum detail.

- 3) **Complexity:** The designing, developing, and maintaining and enabling the large technology to IoT system is quite complicated.

3.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

In proposed system it can able to find owner details from captured image. Efficiency and Performance of new system may decline due to discard of OCR library but the memory requirements will decrease and also the effort for installing, configuring and running the system would decrease. Minimum image angle: 90 degree (looking straight at the license plate). Image should be captured in daylight. The efficiency of the proposed system can be measured only in terms of number plates successfully and correctly recognized which can only be measured upon implementation. Intelligent Parking System can grant permission to access the parking area with less human inference. This system can capture image of the vehicle, identify the type of vehicle and allot best fit and optimal parking slot based on its size. It extracts the vehicle's License plate number, entry time, exit time and calculate total time of the vehicle present with in the parking space. camera is used to identify the Region of Interest, Vehicle license plate and identify the characters from the license plates.

3.2.1 ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

1) Higher Productivity

OCR software helps businesses to achieve higher productivity by facilitating quicker data retrieval when required

2) Cost Reduction

Opting for OCR will help businesses on cutting down on hiring professionals to carry out data extraction, which is one of the most important benefits of OCR data entry methods.

3) High Accuracy

One of the major challenges of data entry is inaccuracy. Automated data entry tools such as OCR data entry result in reduced errors and inaccuracies, resulting in efficient data entry.

4) Disaster Recovery

Disaster recovery is one of the major benefits of using OCR for data entry. When data is stored electronically in secure servers and distributed systems, it remains safe even under emergency situations

3.3 FEASIBILITY STUDY

The feasibility of the project is analyzed in this phase and business proposal is put forth with a very general plan for the project and some cost estimates. During system analysis the feasibility study of the proposed system is to be carried out. This is to ensure that the proposed system is not a burden to the company. For feasibility analysis, some understanding of the major requirements for the system is essential. Three key considerations involved in the feasibility analysis are

1. Economic feasibility
2. Technical feasibility
3. Social feasibility
4. Operational feasibility

3.3.1 ECONOMICAL FEASIBILITY

This study is carried out to check the economic impact that the system will have on the organization. The amount of fund that the company can pour into the research and

development of the system is limited. The expenditures must be justified. Thus the developed system as well within the budget and this was achieved because most of the technologies used are freely available. Only the customized products had to be purchased.

3.3.2 TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY

This study is carried out to check the technical feasibility, that is, the technical requirements of the system. Any system developed must not have a high demand on the available technical resources. This will lead to high demands being placed on the client. A feasibility study evaluates the project's potential for success.

3.3.3 SOCIAL FEASIBILITY

The aspect of study is to check the level of acceptance of the system by the user. This includes the process of training the user to use the system efficiently. The user must not feel threatened by the system, instead must accept it as a necessity. The level of acceptance by the users solely depends on the methods that are employed to educate the user about the system and to make him familiar with it. His level of confidence must be raised so that he is also able to make some constructive criticism, which is welcomed, as he is the final user of the system.

CHAPTER 4

SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

System Architecture is a generic discipline to handle objects (existing or to be created) called “systems”, in a way that supports reasoning about the structural properties of these objects. The system architecture is a response to the conceptual and practical difficulties of the description and the design of complex systems

fig 4.1: System Architecture

4.2 UML DIAGRAMS

UML stands for Unified Modeling Language. UML is a standardized general-purpose modeling language in the field of object-oriented software engineering. The standard is managed, and was created by, the Object Management Group.

The goal is for UML to become a common language for creating models of object oriented computer software. In its current form UML is comprised of two major components: a Meta-model and a notation. In the future, some form of method or process may also be added to; or associated with, UML.

The Unified Modeling Language is a standard language for specifying, Visualization, Constructing and documenting the artifacts of software system, as well as for business modeling and other non-software systems.

The UML represents a collection of best engineering practices that have proven successful in the modeling of large and complex systems.

The UML is a very important part of developing objects oriented software and the software development process. The UML uses mostly graphical notations to express the design of software projects.

GOALS:

The Primary goals in the design of the UML are as follows:

1. Provide users a ready-to-use, expressive visual modeling Language so that they can develop and exchange meaningful models.
2. Provide extendibility and specialization mechanisms to extend the core concepts.
3. Be independent of particular programming languages and development process.
4. Provide a formal basis for understanding the modeling language.
5. Encourage the growth of OO tools market.
6. Support higher level development concepts such as collaborations, frameworks, patterns and components.
7. Integrate best practices.

4.2.1 USE CASE DIAGRAM:

A use case diagram in the Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a type of behavioral diagram defined by and created from a Use-case analysis. Its purpose is to present a graphical overview of the functionality provided by a system in terms of actors, their goals (represented as use cases), and any dependencies between those use cases. The main purpose of a use case diagram is to show what system functions are performed for which actor. Roles of the actors in the system can be depicted.

Fig 4.2 Use Case Diagram

4.2.2 SEQUENCE DIAGRAM:

A sequence diagram in Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a kind of interaction diagram that shows how processes operate with one another and in what order. It is a construct of a Message Sequence Chart. Sequence diagrams are sometimes called event diagrams, event scenarios, and timing diagrams.

Fig 4.3 Sequence Diagram

4.2.3 ACTIVITY DIAGRAM:

Activity diagrams are graphical representations of work flows of stepwise activities and actions with support for choice, iteration and concurrency. In the Unified Modeling Language, activity diagrams can be used to describe the business and operational step-by-step work flows of components in a system. An activity diagram shows the overall flow of control.

Fig 4.4 Activity Diagram

4.2.4 DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

DFD-0

DFD-1

DFD-2

Fig 4.5 Data Flow Diagram

4.2.5 CLASS DIAGRAM

Fig 4.6 Class Diagram

4.2.6 DEPLOYMENT DIAGRAM

Fig 4.7 Deployment Diagram

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

5.1 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

The most common set of requirements defined by any operating system or software application is the physical computer resources, also known as hardware. A hardware requirements list is often accompanied by a hardware compatibility list, especially in case of operating systems. The minimal hardware requirements are as follows,

PROCESSOR : PENTIUM IV

RAM : 8 GB

PROCESSOR : 2.4 GHZ

MAIN MEMORY : 8GB RAM

PROCESSING SPEED : 600 MHZ

HARD DISK DRIVE : 1TB

5.2 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

Software requirements deals with defining resource requirements and prerequisites that needs to be installed on a computer to provide functioning of an application. These requirements are need to be installed separately before the software is installed. The minimal software requirements are as follows,

FRONT END :PYTHON

IDE : ANACONDA

OPERATING SYSTEM :WINDOWS 10

CHAPTER 6

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

6.1 SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

6.1.1 Python Language

Python is an object-oriented programming language created by Guido Rossum in 1989. It is ideally designed for rapid prototyping of complex applications. It has interfaces to many OS system calls and libraries and is extensible to C or C++. Many large companies use the Python programming language include NASA, Google, YouTube, BitTorrent, etc. Python programming is widely used in Artificial Intelligence, Natural Language Generation, Neural Networks and other advanced fields of Computer Science. Python had deep focus on code readability & this class will teach you python from basics.

Python Programming Characteristics

- It provides rich data types and easier to read syntax than any other programming languages
- It is a platform independent scripted language with full access to operating system API's
- Compared to other programming languages, it allows more run-time flexibility
- It includes the basic text manipulation facilities of Perl and Awk
- A module in Python may have one or more classes and free functions
- Libraries in Python's are cross-platform compatible with Linux, Macintosh, and Windows
- For building large applications, Python can be compiled to byte-code

- Python supports functional and structured programming as well as OOP
- It supports interactive mode that allows interacting Testing and debugging of snippets of code
- In Python, since there is no compilation step, editing, debugging and testing is fast.
-

6.1.2 About OpenCV Package

Python is a general purpose programming language started by Guido van Rossum, which became very popular in short time mainly because of its simplicity and code readability. It enables the programmer to express his ideas in fewer lines of code without reducing any readability.

Compared to other languages like C/C++, Python is slower. But another important feature of Python is that it can be easily extended with C/C++. This feature helps us to write computationally intensive codes in C/C++ and create a Python wrapper for it so that we can use these wrappers as Python modules. This gives us two advantages: first, our code is as fast as original C/C++ code (since it is the actual C++ code working in background) and second, it is very easy to code in Python. This is how OpenCV-Python works, it is a Python wrapper around original C++ implementation.

And the support of Numpy makes the task more easier. Numpy is a highly optimized library for numerical operations. It gives a MATLAB-style syntax. All the OpenCV array structures are converted to-and-from Numpy arrays. So whatever operations you can do in Numpy, you can combine it with OpenCV, which increases number of weapons in your arsenal. Besides that, several other libraries like SciPy, Matplotlib which supports Numpy can be used with this.

So OpenCV-Python is an appropriate tool for fast prototyping of computer vision problems.

6.1.3 Anaconda

Anaconda is a free and open source, easy to install distribution of Python and R programming languages. Anaconda provides a working environment which is used for scientific computing, data science, statistical analysis and machine learning.

The latest distribution of Anaconda is Anaconda 5.3 and is released in October, 2018. It has the conda package, environment manager and a collection of 1000+ open source packages long with free community support.

What is Anaconda Navigator?

Anaconda Navigator is a desktop graphical user interface (GUI) included in the Anaconda distribution. It allows us to launch applications provided in the Anaconda distribution and easily manage conda packages, environments and channels without the use of command-line commands. It is available for Windows, macOS and Linux.

Anaconda Navigator

Applications Provided In Anaconda Distribution

The Anaconda distribution comes with the following applications along with Anaconda Navigator.

1. JupyterLab
2. Jupyter Notebook
3. Qt Console
4. Spyder
5. Glueviz
6. Orange3
7. RStudio
8. Visual Studio Code

SQLite

SQLite is not directly comparable to client/server SQL database engines such as MySQL, Oracle, PostgreSQL, or SQL Server since SQLite is trying to solve a different problem.

Client/server SQL database engines strive to implement a shared repository of enterprise data. They emphasize scalability, concurrency, centralization, and control. SQLite strives to provide local data storage for individual applications and devices. SQLite emphasizes economy, efficiency, reliability, independence, and simplicity

SQLite3 can be integrated with Python using `sqlite3` module, which was written by Gerhard Haring. It provides an SQL interface compliant with the DB-API 2.0 specification described by PEP 249. You do not need to install this module separately because it is shipped by default along with Python version 2.5.x onwards.

To use `sqlite3` module, you must first create a connection object that represents the database and then optionally you can create a cursor object, which will help you in executing all the SQL statements.

Python `sqlite3` module APIs

Following are important `sqlite3` module routines, which can suffice your requirement to work with SQLite database from your Python program. If you are looking for a more sophisticated application, then you can look into Python `sqlite3` module's official documentation.

`sqlite3.connect(database [,timeout ,other optional arguments])`

This API opens a connection to the SQLite database file. You can use `":memory:"` to open a database connection to a database that resides in RAM instead of on disk. If database is opened successfully, it returns a connection object.

When a database is accessed by multiple connections, and one of the processes modifies the database, the SQLite database is locked until that transaction is committed. The timeout parameter specifies how long the connection should wait for the lock to go away until raising an exception. The default for the timeout parameter is 5.0 (five seconds).

If the given database name does not exist then this call will create the database. You can specify filename with the required path as well if you want to create a database anywhere else except in the current directory.

connection.cursor([cursorClass])

This routine creates a cursor which will be used throughout of your database programming with Python. This method accepts a single optional parameter cursorClass. If supplied, this must be a custom cursor class that extends sqlite3.

connection.close()

This method closes the database connection. Note that this does not automatically call commit(). If you just close your database connection without calling commit() first, your changes will be lost!

Connect To Database

Following Python code shows how to connect to an existing database. If the database does not exist, then it will be created and finally a database object will be returned.

```
#!/usr/bin/python  
  
import sqlite3  
  
conn = sqlite3.connect('test.db')
```

```
print "Opened database successfully";
```

Here, you can also supply database name as the special name `:memory:` to create a database in RAM. Now, let's run the above program to create our database `test.db` in the current directory. You can change your path as per your requirement. Keep the above code in `sqlite.py` file and execute it as shown below. If the database is successfully created, then it will display the following message.

```
$chmod +x sqlite.py
```

```
$/sqlite.py
```

```
Open database successfully
```

6.2 LIST OF MODULES

- Database entry
- Feature extraction
- Optical character recognition
- Authentication
- Parking slot allocation

6.2.1 DATABASE ENTRY

The database module contains database which is made on SQLite. It stores all the data and entries of the system. It is connected through python. Tables are created on a schema suited to support the system and provide various tables for convenient data storage and retrieval. The system is stand alone and does not require user to carry any device thus making completely automated for the user.

6.2.2 FEATURE EXTRACTION

It is the process of transforming the raw pixel values from an image, to a more meaningful and useful information that can be used in other techniques, such as point matching or machine learning.

In feature extraction module, we will characterize the boxes associated with vehicles by a set of parameters.

This step aims to perform two important tasks:

- Classify vehicles according to their types.
- Detect partial occlusions of vehicles.

6.2.3 OPTICAL CHARACTER RECOGNITION

Optical Character Recognition known as OCR, enabled system will provide an automated system for parking management. And also it will provide the control over the access of parking space For huge parking it will be an effective system. camera is used to identify the Region of Interest, Vehicle license plate and identify the characters from the license plate. Tesseract Engine and Optical Character Recognition (OCR) functions are used to detect characters from the image. The automatic number plate recognition with OCR works by using the technology to capture the images and retrieving the license numbers on the plate. It works by simply highlighting the numbers on the image and separating them from the other objects on the screen. Optical Character Recognition known as OCR, enabled system will provide an automated system for parking management. And also it will provide the control over the access of parking space For huge parking it will be an effective system.

6.2.4 AUTHENTICATION

I. Registered user:

A registered user is a user of a website, program, or other system who has previously registered. Registered users normally provide some sort of credentials (such as a username or e-mail address, and a password) to the system in order to prove their identity: this is known as logging in. Registration is one of the primary modules in any data management system. In case of registered user, the registered user arrives at the parking slot and the vehicle number is scanned as a confirmation message. After verification of the number. Then user is allowed park the vehicle in reserved slot.

II. Un-Registered user:

In case of Un-Registered user, the unregistered user at the entrance of parking area. If the Parking space are available then user need to enter PIN number of the registered users. Then parking slots is provided for them.

6.2.5 PARKING SLOT ALLOCATION

The smart parking system that exploits technologies for parking space availability detection and for driver localization and which optimally allocates and reserves parking spots to drivers instead of only supplying guidance to them. For every successful authentication, the stored information in the database is fetched using SQLite and compared with OCR result to allocate their respective parking slots. Additionally a clock is used to keep track of the time information. The system will show the detail information about the parking slot using this system. This will provide the vacancy for parking the vehicles in a particular parking area.

CHAPTER 7

SYSTEM TESTING

7.1 GENERAL

Testing is performed to identify errors. It is used for quality assurance. Testing is an integral part of the entire development and maintenance process. The goal of the testing during phase is to verify that the specification has been accurately and completely incorporated into the design, as well as to ensure the correctness of the design itself.

For example, the design must not have any logical faults. The fault in the design is detected before coding commences, otherwise the cost of fixing the faults will be considerably higher as reflected. Detection of design faults can be achieved by means of inspection as well as walk through.

7.2 TESTING TECHNIQUES

A test plan is a document which describes approach, its scope, its resources and the schedule of aimed testing exercises. It helps to identify almost other test item, the features which are to be tested, its tasks, how will everyone do each task, how much the tester is independent, the environment in which the test is taking place, its technique of design plus the both the end criteria which is used, also rational of choice of theirs, and whatever kind of risk which requires emergency planning. It can be also referred to as the record of the process of test planning. Test plans are usually prepared with signification input from test engineers.

7.2.1 UNIT TESTING

In unit testing, the design of the test cases is involved that helps in the validation of the internal program logic. The validation of all the decision branches and internal code takes place. After the individual unit is completed it takes place. Plus it is taken

into account after the individual unit is completed before integration. The unit test thus performs the basic level test at its component stage and test the particular business process, system configurations etc. The unit test ensures that the particular unique path of the process gets performed precisely to the documented specifications and contains clearly defined inputs with the results which are expected.

7.2.2 INTEGRATION TESTING

These tests are designed to test the integrated software items to determine whether if they really execute as a single program or application. The testing is event driven and thus is concerned with the basic outcome of field. The Integration tests demonstrate that the components were individually satisfaction, as already represented by successful unit testing, the components are apt and fine. This type of testing is specially aimed to expose the issues that come-up by the components combination.

7.2.3 FUNCTIONAL TESTING

The functional tests help in providing the systematic representation that functions tested are available and specified by technical requirement, documentation of the system and the user manual.

7.2.4 SYSTEM TESTING

System testing, as the name suggests, is the type of testing in which ensure that the software system meet the business requirements and aim. Testing of the configuration is taken place here to ensure predictable result and thus analysis of it. System testing is relied on the description of process and its flow, stressing on pre driven process and the points of integration.

7.2.5 WHITE BOX TESTING

This testing is also called as Glass box testing. In this testing, by knowing the specific functions that a product has been designed to perform test can be conducted that demonstrate each function is fully operational at the same time searching for errors in each function. It is a test case design method that uses the control structure of the procedural design to derive test cases. Basis path testing is white box testing.

- Basis path testing:
- Flow graph notation
- Cyclometric complexity
- Deriving test cases
- Graph matrices control

7.2.6 BLACK BOX TESTING

In this testing by knowing the internal operation of a product, test can be conducted to ensure that “all gears mesh”, that is the internal operation performs according to specification and all internal components have been adequately exercised. It fundamentally focuses on the functional requirements of the software. The steps involved in black box test case design are:

- Graph based testing methods
- Equivalence partitioning
- Boundary value analysis
- Comparison testing

7.2.7 ACCEPTANCE TESTING

User Acceptance Testing is a critical phase of any project and requires significant participation by the end user. It also ensures that the system meets the functional requirements.

CHAPTER 8

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The proposed method consists of two main phases which are plate localization/detection and character recognition. OCR is the most important component in the system, which is responsible for recognizing the characters in the license plate and converting them into machine-readable format. The following steps are carried out to achieve the desired recognition process:

- (1) Converting the image into gray scale.
- (2) License Plate localization.
- (3) Character segmentation.

The proposed technology can play an important role in improvements in present-day vehicle parking management systems.

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, the presented methodology is effectively able to fee generation best fit and optimal parking area to the vehicle based on its QR code. It can be able extract features like number plate. It performs machine learning operations like Haar cascade to detect dimensions of car. Future work the Extracted feature can likewise be utilized to prepare neural system for higher precision. In acknowledgment, as well much variety in character geometry prompts misclassification. So as to reduce these, classifier is should be trained with various character textual styles which was detected from individual training data set

.In Future, Android based application can be developed for polling the parking status from the sensor networks deployed in parking lots, the reservation status is affected by the change of physical parking status. The drivers are allowed to access the server on their Android smart phones.

APPENDICES

A. Sample Code

```
from flask import Flask

from flask import request, redirect, render_template, url_for

from werkzeug.utils import secure_filename

import os

import pytesseract

from PIL import ImageFilter

from PIL import Image

import sys

#reload(sys)

#sys.setdefaultencoding("utf-8")

app = Flask(__name__)

app.config['UPLOAD_FOLDER'] = './media'

@app.route('/')

def index():

    return render_template('index.html')
```

```

@app.route('/submitImage/',methods=['POST',])

def submitImage():

    image = request.files['ocrImage']

    text = ''

    filename = secure_filename(image.filename)

    image.save(os.path.join(app.config['UPLOAD_FOLDER'], filename))

    img = Image.open(os.path.join(app.config['UPLOAD_FOLDER'], filename))

    text = pytesseract.image_to_string(img)

    print(text)

    f = open(os.path.join(app.config['UPLOAD_FOLDER'], filename)+'.txt','w')

    f.write(text)

    f.close()

    return render_template('textFile.html',text=text,filename=f)

if __name__ == '__main__':

    app.run(debug=True)

```

Header file

Flask & pil is a library..

```
from flask import Flask
```

```
from flask import request,redirect,render_template,url_for
```

```
from werkzeug.utils import secure_filename
```

```
import os
```

```
import pytesseract
```

```
from PIL import ImageFilter
```

```
from PIL import Image
```

This one line can change image words into text

```
text = pytesseract.image_to_string(img)
```

B. Sreenshots

1. Vehicle owner registration:

Registration

<input type="text"/>
Username
<input type="password"/>
Password
<input type="text"/>
Enter your phone number
<input type="text"/>
Email
<input type="text"/>
Two Wheeler
<input type="text"/>
Vehicle Number
<input type="text"/>
Account number
<input type="text"/>
Enter IFSC1

2. User Login Module :

3. Vehicle image capture

4. Processing the image using OCR

REFERENCES

1. Automatic Parking Space Detection System
Authors: Nazia Bibi ; Muhammad Nadeem Majid ; Hassan Dawood ; Ping Guo, Year: 2017
2. Software Design of Automatic Parking Robot Based on Flat Stereo Garage
Authors: Dapeng Wang ; Jianwei Ye ; Chence Guo.
Year: 2019
3. License Plate Detection and Integral Intensity Projection for Automatic Finding the Vacant of Car Parking Space
Authors: P. Choorat ; C. Sirikornkarn ; T. Pramoun.
Year:2019
4. Automatic Car Parking System Using Raspberry-Pi with Cloud Storage Environment
Authors: R Aswini. ; T Archana,
Year: 2019
5. AU Automatic Car-Parking Modeling System
Authors: Narong Apheratsakun ; Lam Thanh Duy ; Jiradech Kongthon.
Year: 2018
6. Automatic Parking Trajectory Planning Based on Recurrent Neural Network
Authors: Zhonghan Wang ; Qingliang Shao ; Chen Wang ; Qian Zhang.
Year: 2018